

Figure 6. Effect of paclitaxel 1 μ M on mDRGs cultured in microfluidic chambers. (a) Treatment and assays timeline (b)–(c) Representative traces of responsive neurons. Y axes represents fluorescence normalized to somal KCl response. (d) Percentage of response normalized to Did+ and somal KCl+ responsive cells. Mean \pm SEM. (e)–(h) Responses to capsaicin and menthol, menthol and AITC or capsaicin and AITC normalized to somal KCl response. (i) Size of the response normalized to KCl. Mean \pm SEM, every dot represents a cell. Statistical analysis two-tailed Mann-Whitney U. $N = 5$ animals, three males and two females; $n \geq 2$ coverslips per animal; total number of crossing neurons = 1638.

functional neurons, activated by capsaicin, menthol, AITC and KCl (Figures 6(b)–(d)). Similarly, terminals responding to two agonists was mildly affected by the chemotherapeutic drug (Figures 6(e)–(H)). In marked contrast, we observed a significant increase in the size of capsaicin responses at DIV eight that resolved at DIV 10 in agreement with previous results (Figure 6(i)).²⁸ Menthol responses show a tendency to increase 48 h after paclitaxel exposure but did not reach statistical significance. Nonetheless, the cellular distribution suggests the presence of two menthol sensitive subpopulations that

deserves further investigation. Higher responses for AITC were observed 96 h (DIV 10) after paclitaxel incubation. Overall, these results substantiate a peripheral action of paclitaxel sensitizing neural endings, consistent with the sensory symptoms provoked by the chemotherapeutic drug.

Conclusions and perspectives

Our findings substantiate that compartmentalized sensory neurons in microfluidic chambers are suitable models to